

1 **CDK10 compensates for ERBB2 inhibition and is associated with trastuzumab resistance.**

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6 Treatment failure in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is associated with progression to CNS
7 metastasis. We recently defined the full complement of kinases and phosphatases whose expression
8 defines the HER2+ subtype tumor in humans with breast cancer, and demonstrated separately that
9 quantitative determination of differential expression was sufficient for identification of synthetic lethality and
10 kinase addiction. We demonstrate here from study of RNA-sequencing measurement of total transcription
11 following pharmacologic inhibition of ERBB2 with two separate HER2 kinase inhibitors in human cancer
12 cells *in vitro* that CDK10 is compensatorily up-regulated in response to ERBB2 inhibition. Accordingly,
13 CDK10 induction was observed *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients who failed treatment with
14 trastuzumab (resistance). CDK10 compensates for ERBB2 inhibition. We argue CDK10 adjunctive
15 inhibition is a viable option for reversal or prevention of resistance to trastuzumab.
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Results

We studied total transcription in human cancer cells treated with small molecule inhibitors of the kinase encoded by *ERBB2*, HER2, to identify kinases activated by the cancer cell to compensate for HER2 kinase inhibition.

Figure 1: Treatment of prostate cancer cells with the first generation HER2 inhibitor lapatinib results in compensatory induction of CDK10.

GSE199800

n=6 DU145 (control: *n*=3 untreated and *n*=3 DMSO treated)

n=2 DU145 treated with lapatinib

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	0.08537697	0.203	-1.7203052	-0.3493253	306.19	CDK10	498/11449	95.7

Figure 2: Treatment of breast cancer cells with the second generation HER2 inhibitor neratinib results in compensatory induction of CDK10.

GSE249573

n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; DMSO treated)

n=4 MDA-MB-453 and HCC1954 (*n*=2 each; control; neratinib treated)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	3.04E-03	0.0548	-2.9633915	-0.1624729	2008.4	CDK10	503/19129	97.4

Pharmacologic inhibition of the HER2 kinase in cancer cells resulted in induction of CDK10 (Figure 1 and 2). Next, we measured total transcription *in vivo* in HER2+ breast cancer patients who had developed resistance to treatment with the HER2+ monoclonal antibody trastuzumab (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CDK10 is transcriptionally activated *in vivo* in HER2+ patients who have developed resistance to trastuzumab.

GSE162187

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment sensitive

n=4 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab; treatment resistant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8558	4.88E-02	0.583	-1.9705226	-1.1495699	929.14	CDK10	1202/19507	93.8

GSE20194

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab (pCR)

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer treated with trastuzumab with residual disease (RD)

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203469_s_at	0.00068315	-5.0648812	-0.01304	-2.4612	CDK10	135/22283	99.4

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Discussion

We demonstrated here through measurement of total transcription in cancer cells treated with small molecule inhibitors of the HER2 kinase lapatinib and neratinib that CDK10 is compensatorily activated in response to HER2 inhibition. Consistent with CDK10 activation in response to pharmacologic inhibition of HER2, we found CDK10 transcriptional induction in the tumors of patients with HER2+ breast cancer that had developed resistance to the HER2-targeted monoclonal antibody trastuzumab. Co-administration of a CDK10 inhibitor with senescence-inducing CDK4/6 inhibitors (manuscript in preparation) that target senescence-associated *CDKN* expression as a general mechanism by which cancer cells resist treatment with chemotherapy (manuscript in preparation) is a viable strategy to counteract resistance to trastuzumab.